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Title: Crisis-Induced Hospital Financial Performance and Quality of Care: Evidence From Portugal

Category: Efficiency Measurement in Healthcare

Objectives: The recent economic crisis has had a profound impact on individual health and healthcare systems triggering variations in population health and income all around Europe. In Portugal its effect was aggravated by austerity measures taken in response to economic conditions leading to changes in hospital budgets and capacities. While the relationship between the crisis and healthcare utilization has been addressed in the literature, its impact on the quality of care remains an open empirical question. This study aims at investigating the impact of the crisis induced financial hardship on the evolution of the quality of hospital care in Portugal distinguishing between demand-side and supply-side effects.

Methods: The study conducts a comprehensive analysis of hospital care quality indicators currently in use across European countries. Next, the paper combines local municipality level data and hospital-level financial condition data with hospital-level DRG data for Portugal for the period 2012-2017 and conducts a multivariate regression analysis to infer the demand and supply-side effects of the crisis-induced changes in hospital financial performance on the evolution of quality of hospital services provided. We perform the analysis accounting for the severity of health outcomes across several domains of hospital care, namely mental health and acute care with high and low mortality outcomes, thereby examining impact of the hospital financial performance in the aftermath of the economic crisis on a range of hospital care quality indicators derived from the DRG data, including mortality rates, waiting times, hospital readmissions, patient safety related measures and other quality indicators identified in the literature.

Results: Preliminary results show that the economic crisis prompted a higher utilization of hospital care services in nearly all of its domains in Portugal, suggesting a possibility of foregone or postponed preventive and primary care. Meanwhile, the study indicates statistically significant relationship between hospital financial performance and quality of care indicators. Economic hardship at the hospital level appears to be associated with lower length of inpatient stays, which may imply either increased efficiency or decreased quality of short-term hospital services thereby highlighting need for further investigation.

Discussion: The findings of the study suggest that both supply and demand side effects contributed to the evolution of quality, however the effects were heterogeneous depending on the domain of hospital care, and that more investigation is needed to understand the mechanisms behind these processes.